

PERFORMANCE OF DARK I-V TESTS TO DETERMINE THE CONDITION OF SPACECRAFT SOLAR ARRAYS

Edward M. Gaddy
Goddard Space Flight Center, Greenbelt, MD 20771

ABSTRACT

Dark I-V tests are sometimes used to determine the condition of spacecraft solar arrays. This is particularly true in cases where the array is mounted to the spacecraft such that some or all of the array cannot be illuminated. This paper shows that these tests are unable to find even significant damage to arrays and for the most part serve only as continuity checks. This is shown to be the case from both theory and experiment.

THEORY

From a theoretical perspective it is difficult to find a cracked solar cell using a dark I-V curve test. Figure 1 with the following text explains why.

Fig. 1. Simplified Solar Cell Model

The widely used solar cell model [1] shown in Figure 1 is basically a constant current source, represented by the circle containing the upward pointing arrow and by the symbol J_L , across a diode. The quantity of current produced by the current source is proportional to the intensity of light on the cell. The current through the diode is denoted by J_D . If a solar cell cracks, so that a part of the cell is no longer in the circuit, the current source reduces output by the proportion of the cell that is removed by the crack. However, the remaining part of the cell still has a diode that has a current versus voltage characteristic virtually identical to the diode that existed before the crack.

When the cell is illuminated, there is no difficulty seeing the results of a crack. The cell simply reduces its current output at any operating voltage by the amount of area the crack removes. If the cell is in series with other cells, it is still easy to see the effects in the string I-V curve. If the string of solar cells is at open circuit voltage, no effect is seen. As the load resistance is decreased there is practically no effect on the string output until the cracked cell reaches its short circuit current, which is less than the short circuit current of the other cells. As the load resistance further decreases, the cracked cell cannot pass additional current through its constant current source. Its diode therefore reverses while the constant current source keeps the string current output at the reduced short circuit current of the damaged cell. Eventually, the diode starts leaking current and the shunt resistance R_{SH} starts to pass current. As the cell goes further into reverse, the diode will break down and allow more current to pass. This gives the string I-V curve the distinctive shape shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Output of a Series String of Silicon Solar Cells With and Without a Cracked Solar Cell

However, in the dark, the string's I - V curve does not show such a significant difference. Even the cell I - V curve is qualitatively identical to the I - V curve obtained on an

uncracked cell because only the diode part of the cell functions. The constant current source is no longer involved. Ignoring the small effect R_{SH} , the only differences are that the diode is operating at a higher current density and the series resistance is increased. This means that the cracked cell curve will have a slightly higher voltage for a given current than the whole cell curve. These effects are shown in Figure 3 for a silicon solar cell with a nominal short circuit current of 0.31 amperes and a nominal open circuit voltage of 0.542 volts. The Figure 3 curve with the lower voltage represents the dark I-V curve without a crack. The Figure 3 curve with the higher voltage represents the same cell with one third of its area lost due to a crack. The higher voltage is due to increased current density in the diode plus a thirty-three percent increase in the estimated 0.3 ohm series resistance of the cell. Please note that the cell represented by Figure 3 is not the same size cell used in the circuit represented by Figure 2.

Fig. 3. I-V Curves from a Dark Solar Cell Without a Crack and With One Third of the Cell Area Lost to a Crack

In a typical solar array the cell may be in series with on the order of 100 solar cells. If current is passed through such a circuit the cracked cell will be undetectable. This is because, from Figure 3, the dark I-V curve will increase the voltage of the circuit only about 0.04 volts at 0.31 amperes forward current as against a circuit without cracked cells. The voltage of the circuit with no cracked cells will be on the order of 54.2 volts at 0.31 amperes. The 0.04 volt increase therefore represents a change of 0.07%. Further, the voltage of the circuit decreases as a function of temperature at a rate of about 0.22 volts per degrees Celsius. So the 0.04 volt increase could be interpreted as a decrease in temperature of the circuit of about 0.2 degree Celsius. Further complicating the assessment is that the current being passed through the circuit may have some self heating effect. The possibility of detecting a crack, or even several cracks in a series circuit of cells is therefore negligible.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A circuit on the qualification panel for the XTE solar array provided an opportunity to verify the theoretical conclusion drawn above. This 103 series cell circuit had a solar cell with a crack, shown in Figure 4. This crack had no effect on the output of the circuit at temperatures below about 40C. However, at higher temperatures, the crack opened such that the bottom triangular section of the cracked cell electrically disconnected from the rest of the cell. This opening and closing of the crack could be accomplished reliably and repeatedly by raising and lowering the panel's temperature. This was verified by measuring the illuminated output of the panel before, during and after exposure to the elevated temperature. The results always showed a dramatic change in the shape of the I-V curve between 28C and 40C, see Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Cracked Cell on the XTE Qualification Solar Panel Dimensions in Centimeters

Fig. 5. I-V Curves from the XTE Qualification Panel at 28C, 40C, 50C and 60C

However, attempting to find the defect by using a dark I-V curves, as shown in Figure 6 was completely unsuccessful. Figure 6 shows no sign of a defect at any temperature.

Fig. 6. Dark I-V Curves from the XTE Solar Panel at 22C, 40C, 50C, and 60C

As predicted the Figure 6 curve shapes give no indication that the cells are broken. Further, the voltage difference between the 22C and the 40C curves at 0.9 amperes amounts to -.22 volts per degree Celsius. The voltage difference between the 40C curve and the 50C curve at 0.9 amperes is -.21 volts per degree Celsius. The difference in these values are within experimental error. Thus, these values are of no help in determining whether a circuit has a broken cell.

PREVIOUS RESULTS

Results from other authors have been obtained that bear on the question of whether dark I-V curves can be used to determine if circuits or strings are totally missing from a spacecraft solar array. Rauschenbach makes this statement regarding such an application: "These [results] . . . indicate that the dark I-V characteristics cannot be used to adequately determine the number of modules connected in the circuit,

except for major discrepancies." [2] This statement related to a particular case where twenty modules were in parallel. With fewer parallel elements, the task would be easier.

Recent work has demonstrated that an alternative method to dark I-V testing exists. Capacitance testing can detect the loss of about 25% of a solar cell in a string of 40 cells [4]. While this level of detectability still presents formidable problems for more than 40 series cells, it is significantly more sensitive than dark I-V curves.

CONCLUSIONS

Dark I-V curves have been used to assess the health of spacecraft solar arrays for some time. They are used in cases where it is difficult or virtually impossible to illuminate the array. This frequently happens when the array is folded against the spacecraft or itself. Unfortunately, this paper and earlier results show that the test cannot find even substantial damage to solar cells and depending on the array configuration even has difficulty determining whether entire strings are missing. Recent work has shown that capacitance testing of spacecraft solar arrays offers a potential alternative.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Rauschenbach, *Solar Cell Array Design Handbook*, Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., New York, 1980, p. 55.
- [2] *Ibid.*, p. 392.
- [3] M. S. Imamura, P. Brandtzaeg and J. L. Miller, "Solar Cell Dark I-V Characteristics and their Applications," in *Proceedings of ENERGY 70 Intersociety Energy Conversion Engineering Conference*, 1970.
- [4] R. L. Mueller, M. T. Wallace, and D. R. Burger, JPL New Technology Report on "Solar Array Performance Check by Measurement of String Capacitance," NPO-19624, February 1995.